

Development of Massive MIMO antenna for mm-wave application

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Abstract— This antenna is designed for wide bandwidth operation and satisfied for multiband operation. This antenna has different various shapes radiating element developed for 6 GHz frequency as an mm-wave. The various shape cut slot are introduce for radiating elements to improve bandwidth and multiband operation of an antenna. These radiating elements are placed very nearer, therefore, it increases isolation amounts the radiating elements, that effects on the performance of an antenna and its parameter such as correlation coefficient (CC), envelop correlation coefficient (ECC), total active reflection coefficient (TARC) and diversity gain (DG). To improve the isolation parameter, a defected ground structure (DGS) technique is introduced within the ground plane of an antenna. This defects introduce by DGS is rectangular in nature. It improves the isolation that is less than -10dB and further improves bandwidth; Therefore, antenna works in wideband operation. The lowest values of performance parameter are obtained for an antenna such as a CC, ECC, TARC and DG. The bandwidth is improved to 98 MHz (1.63%). The massive MIMO antenna is developed using parasitic elements for wide bandwidth and multiband operation. Parasitic element is used between the radiating elements which has different structure. The parasitic elements are introduced for improvement of antenna parameter, such as isolation, CC, ECC, DG and TARC.

Keywords— DGS, MIMO, CC, ECC, DG and TARC.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless systems have seen significant development in the past few years. There are various applications for wireless technology nowadays, namely, Wi-max, satellite communication, WLAN, 4G, 5G, mobile communications [1], etc. These systems has improved functionality such as, a fast data rate, a huge capacity, greater performance, and reduced multi-path fading. The capacity of a wireless network is influenced by its bandwidth. Therefore, bandwidth should be increased in order to increase the system capacity. The multi-path fading effect [2] is, therefore, necessary for single antenna systems to function properly. As a result, they have a small capacity and band width. The development of multi input and multi output (MIMO) antennas for transmission and receiving applications helps to overcome the limitations of single antenna systems. The design of MIMO antennas has been the focus of in-depth research as a result. Technology for multiple antennas (MIMO) at inputs and output side is the most crucial advancement for next generation wireless communications. The term “multi input and multi output” refer to multiple antennas used for transmitter and receiver to enhance communication. Next generation unguided communications standards are taking into consideration MIMO systems in large part because they offer improvements in data throughput and connection range without additional power requirement, high spectral efficiency, and reduced fading. Antenna performance is crucial in the modern environment to achieve wide bandwidth and higher isolation characteristics. Researchers have been pushed to use wideband antennas for improvement for the design of the microstrip antenna that are used in MIMO system configuration. Research on multiple antennas has been increasingly popular in recent years due to a requirement of higher transmission rates, large bandwidth, and multi-band operation. When large number of antenna components are used in both transmitter side and the receiver side then channel capacity of the system increase [3], [4]. Due to wireless device space limitations, isolation between elements is a critical design issue. Thus, isolation between the antenna components determines the performance characteristics of MIMO antennas, including CC, ECC, TARC and DG, and channel capacity. Because antenna elements are tightly connected to one another, maintaining low isolation between them is a serious issue [5], [6]. Designing a MIMO antenna that uses a multi-band frequency is another necessity for wireless systems. Consequently, it is difficult to build a multi-band antenna. When transmission and reception take place at various frequencies, then there is a requirement of multi-band antenna need to be developed. Thus, a wireless system nowadays needs twin or multi-band antennas.

Therefore, the development of multiband antennas has been a recent research area of interest. High isolation between the many resonant bands, small dimensions, and high efficiency are the three main challenges in constructing a wide band antenna.

II. ANTENNA DESIGN

The 8-element antenna is designed for 6 GHz operation. This antenna consists of eight distinct radiating component, each having a rectangular-shaped cut slot, as shown in Fig. 1. The geometrical structure of an antenna is shown in Fig. 2. The radiating component has a length of 11.34 mm and its width is 15.21 mm. The antenna structure is designed using an FR-4 substrate. The radiating elements are near to each other, the isolation between the patches is increases. As a result, the antenna's performance degrades. Therefore, there is a need to improve the isolation. The combination of parasitic element and DGS [7]-[9] is used for the improvement of isolation.

Fig. 1 MIMO antenna with a parasitic element

Fig. 2 Dimensions of an antenna structure

TABLE I
THE GEOMETRICAL STRUCTURE OF AN ANTENNA

Sr. No.	Parameter	Values of parameter (in mm)
1	Width of a radiating component	A = 15.214
2	Length of a radiating component	B = 11.34
3	Width (W_{IFL}) of the IFL	D = 2.94
4	Length (L_{IFL}) of the IFL	C = 6.387
5	Width (W_{cs}) of a cut slot	D = 2.94
6	Length (L_{cs}) of a cut slot	C = 6.387
7	Width of a P_1 to P_6	D = 2.94
8	Length of a P_1 to P_6	B = 11.34
9	Width of a P_7 to P_{10}	A = 15.21
10	Length of a P_7 to P_{10}	D = 2.94

A rectangular shaped transmission line model is used to develop patch-1 to patch-8 of the radiating component [10], [11]. The patch-2 and patch-4 introduces two rectangular shaped cut slots [12], [13], patch-5 and patch-6 introduces a one rectangular shaped cut slot, while the remaining patches (Patch-1, patch-3, patch-7, and patch-8) have no cut slots. The cut slots have a length of 6.387 mm and its width is 2.94 mm. Rectangular shaped Parasitic elements P_1 to P_{10} are placed between the radiating elements to improve isolation [14]-[19]. The parasitic element P_1 to P_6 has a length of 11.34 mm and a width of 2.942 mm, whereas a parasitic element P_7 to P_{10} has a length of 2.942mm and a width of 15.21 mm. The dimensions of the antenna structure are as shown in Table 1. The use of DGS techniques is another method for enhancing isolation between the radiating components [20]-[25]. Fig.3 represents a ground structure of the antenna. Fig. 4 represents dimensions of the ground structure.

Fig. 3 Ground plane (Back side) of a MIMO antenna

TABLE III
THE GEOMETRICAL STRUCTURE OF AN ANTENNA

Sr. No.	Parameter	Values of parameter (in mm)
1	Width	$E = 74$
2	Length	$F = 36.522$
3	Length of DGS-1 and DGS-8	$G = 5.884$
4	Width of DGS-1 and DGS-8	$C = 6.38$

A rectangular shaped structure is implemented as DGS-1 to DGS 8 in the ground plane. Table 2 shows the dimensions of the DGS-1 to DGS-8. The DGS has a length (G) of 5.884 mm and a width (C) of 6.38 mm. The ground plane has a length of 36.522 mm (F) and a width of 74 mm (E).

Fig. 4 Dimensions of a ground plane (GP)

III.METHODOLOGY

The MIMO antenna is composed of multiple radiating elements. They are placed relatively near to each other. Therefore, isolation amounts radiating element is very high. It affects the performance parameter of an antenna. Therefore, it is necessary to improve isolation using DGS method. A DGS method is nothing but a ground plane defect in an antenna [27]. In the ground plane, cuts slot are introduced which is referred as DGS. The dimensions of ground plane (substrate) of an antenna and rectangular shaped cuts slot are listed in Table 2. Due to introduction of DGS in an antenna the inductor and capacitor is changes, that affects the frequency response of an antenna. The ground plane is modified to enhance its system performance. It is modified using the cut slot, which is called as the DGS [27]. The DGS is acts as a resonant slot, which is aligned with the transmission line model that provides an efficient coupling in the line. Therefore, the DGS is used to enhance the antenna characteristics i.e., size reduction, gain, bandwidth and mutual coupling. A DGS technique is used to improve the isolation. It is necessary in DGS to choose the correct size, shape, the number of structures to be use and the optimal placement of the DGS.

The placement of parasitic elements [28-29] between the antenna elements to partially (or mainly) cancel the coupled fields between them is another method for increasing isolation, and cross correlation of MIMO antenna. As a result of the parasitic element does create an opposite coupling field that weakens the original one, therefore antenna's overall coupling will be reduced. In most cases, these parasitic elements are either not physically attached to the antenna component, like those in, or they are attached to the ground plane to create a resonator. These elements are intended to regulate the bandwidth, maximum coupling reduction, and isolation frequency band.

IV. RESULT ANALYSIS

The designed antenna operates on a multiband frequency and wide bandwidth. The parasitic elements in the rectangular dimension are utilized between the radiating elements to increase the isolation. According to the antenna study, the return loss and associated isolation of a patch-1 to patch-8 are measured at -10dB line.

Fig. 5 Return loss and associated isolation

The patch-1 analysis is depicted in Fig. 5. It operates on a single frequency band, namely, 5.7 GHz. The investigation of patch-1 shows -16.37 dB return loss (S_{11}) and -13.36 dB isolation (S_{15}). The obtained bandwidth is 305.04 MHz (5.084%).

The patch-2 analysis is shown in Fig. 5. It operates on a single frequency band, namely, 7.5 GHz. Its study shows -14.77 dB return loss (S_{22}) and -20.85 dB isolation (S_{26}). The resulting bandwidth is a 105.30MHz (1.755%).

Fig. 6 Return loss and associated isolation

The patch-3 analysis is illustrated in Fig. 6. It operates on a single frequency band, namely, 5.8 GHz. Its analysis finds -16.13 dB return loss (S_{33}) and -12.32 dB isolation (S_{37}). The obtained bandwidth is 315 MHz (5.25%).

The patch-4 analysis is shown in Fig. 6. It works on a single frequency band, namely, 7.5 GHz. Its study indicates -11.55 dB return loss (S_{44}) and -23.22 dB isolation (S_{48}). The resulting bandwidth is 145.50 MHz (2.425%).

The patch-5 analysis is depicted in Fig. 7. The patch-5 operates on a single frequency band, namely, 6.2 GHz. Its analysis shows -19.29 dB return loss (S_{55}) and -12.71 dB isolation (S_{51}). The obtained bandwidth is 309.60 MHz (5.16%).

Fig. 7 Return loss and associated isolation

The patch-6 analysis is shown in Fig. 7. It works on a single frequency band, namely, 6 GHz. Its study indicates that it has -17.16 dB return loss (S_{66}) and -11.35 dB isolation (S_{62}). The resulting bandwidth is 353.4 MHz (6.08%).

Fig. 8 Return loss and associated isolation

The patch-7 analysis is shown in Fig. 8. It operates on a single frequency band, namely, 5.9 GHz. Its analysis finds that it has -21.68dB return loss (S_{77}) and -12.26 dB isolation (S_{76}). The resulting bandwidth is 364.8 MHz (6.08%).

The patch-8 analysis is depicted in Fig. 8. It operates on a single frequency band, namely, 5.8 GHz. Its analysis finds that it has -23.16 dB return loss (S_{88}) and -12.59 dB isolation (S_{85}). The resulting bandwidth is 351 MHz (5.85%).

Fig. 9 VSWR of a radiating patches

The VSWR (V_1 to V_8) values for a antennas patch-1 to patch-8 are presented in Fig. 9. The values range from 1.20 dB to 2.73 dB, as indicated in Table 3.

TABLE III
THE GEOMETRICAL STRUCTURE OF AN ANTENNA

Sr. No.	Parameter	Frequency (GHz)	VSWR (dB)	Absolute Values
1	Patch-1 (V_1)	5.7	2.66	1.84
2	Patch-2 (V_2)	7.5	3.2	2.08
3	Patch-3 (V_3)	5.8	2.73	1.87
4	Patch-4 (V_4)	7.5	4.70	2.95
5	Patch-5 (V_5)	6.2	1.89	1.54
6	Patch-6 (V_6)	6	2.42	1.74
7	Patch-7 (V_7)	5.9	1.43	1.38
8	Patch-8 (V_8)	5.8	1.20	1.31

Fig. 10 represent 3-D pattern of the antenna gain. Fig. 11 represent 3-D pattern of the antenna directivity. The antenna analysis shows 1.34 dB gain and 3.24 dB directivity.

Fig. 10 Gain of the antenna

Fig. 11 Directivity of the antenna

Fig. 12 depicts the antenna’s radiation pattern. $G_1 = 1.34$ dB, $G_2 = 1.16$ dB and $G_3 = 1.34$ dB gains are measured at $\phi = 0^\circ$, $\phi = 90^\circ$ and $\phi = 180^\circ$, respectively.

The antenna’s E-H fields are seen in Fig. 13 At $\theta = 0^\circ$, E_ϕ is measured, and at $\theta = 90^\circ$, H_ϕ is measured.

Fig. 12 Gain of the antenna

Fig. 13 E-H plane of the antenna

The result of antenna shows that a TARC, CC, ECC and DG which are 0.146 (-8.35 dB), 0.0110, less than 0.00012 and close to 10.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The eight-differently shaped massive MIMO antenna uses a parasitic elements and a defective ground structure for an mm-wave application at 6 GHz. A rectangular cut slot is introduced in the radiating patches for multiband functioning, acting as a filter circuit that passes the intended frequency. Utilizing the DGS and a parasitic element, antenna parameter such as isolation, cross correlation, and TARC are improved. The antenna operates at a broad bandwidth on the multiband frequencies of 5.7 GHz, 5.8 GHz, 5.9 GHz, 6.0 GHz, 6.2 GHz, and 7.5 GHz. The analysis of an antenna parameter shows that the return loss, isolation, TARC, CC, ECC, DG and bandwidth obtained are less than -11.40 dB, less than -11.20 dB, less than 0.146 (-8.35 dB), less than 0.0110, less than 0.00012, close to 10 and greater than 100MHz respectively. The gain of antenna is 1.34 dB, and directivity is 3.24 dB. The absolute VSWR values vary from 1.31 to 2.95.

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